

Lignans of *Guaiacum officinale* L. : Photo-sensitized Aerial Oxidation of 2,5-Diaryl-3,4-dimethylfurans and a Novel Method of Sequential Introduction of Alkoxy Functions in Their 3- and 4-Methyl Groups[†]

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From the polar extractives of 'lignum vitae', the heartwood of *Guaiacum officinale*, were isolated two new lignans, designated furoguaiacidin and furoguaiacidin, as their respective diethyl ether derivatives 1a and 2a. The structures of these lignans were established as 2,5-bis(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxy)-3-methoxymethyl-4-methylfuran (1b) and 1,4-bis(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxy)-2,3-dimethyl-*cis*-2-ene-1,4-dione (2b) respectively, from detailed spectral and chemical evidence including partial synthesis of their respective diethyl ether derivatives 1a and 2a from diethylfuroguaiacin (1c) [2,5-bis(4'-ethoxy-3'-methoxy)-3,4-dimethylfuran], the diethyl ether of the congener lignan, furoguaiacin (1d). Prolonged hydrogenolysis of 1a over 10% Pd/C gave 1c, while hydrogenation of 2a over 10% Pd/C afforded, a mixture of 1c and its tetrahydro derivative 1e. The *cis*-configuration of 2a was established by its thermal conversion to the *trans*-isomer 3, reconvertible to 2a on irradiation with uv light, and also by the conversion of 2a to 3 on heating with methanolic NaOH. Unlike 3, 2a underwent facile reductive cyclization to 1c with NaBH₄ and Na₂S₂O₃ or Na₂SO₃ in acidic medium. Both 2a and 3 were smoothly reduced by zinc and HOAc to give predominantly 1c and their 2,3-dihydro derivative 9a as the minor product. Oxidation of 1c with singlet oxygen, produced *in situ* by bubbling air through an ethanolic solution of 1c containing the photosensitizer eosin and exposed to ordinary light, gave 2a in almost quantitative yield. This conversion has also been achieved with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid in fairly good yield. When heated with methanolic H₂SO₄, 2a afforded 1a which was converted to 3,4-bis(methoxymethyl) analog 1f of 1c by bubbling air through an ethanolic solution of 1a in presence of eosin followed by treatment of the product with methanolic H₂SO₄. In an analogous manner, 3-ethoxymethyl and 3,4-bis(ethoxymethyl) analogs 1g and 1h of 1c were prepared from 2a in about 90% yield. This has provided a novel method of sequential introduction of alkoxy functions in the 3- and 4-methyl groups of 2,5-diaryl-3,4-dimethylfurans. Plausible mechanisms of the reactions stated above are discussed.

The heartwood of *Guaiacum officinale* L. (Fam : Zygophyllaceae), popularly known as 'lignum vitae', is reported for its use as a heavy durable commercial timber and for various medicinal applications. The high resin content of *G. officinale* (18–25% of the wood) has long been the subject of great chemical interest. Chemical investigation of the light petroleum extract of 'lignum vitae' resulted earlier in the isolation of as many as nine lignans¹ of different structural types. Our interest² in the lignans of Indian medicinal plants prompted us to examine chemically the extractives of 'lignum vitae' with polar solvents. This has resulted in the isolation from the methanolic extract of the above material (defatted) of two more new lignans, designated furoguaiacidin and furoguaiacidin, as their respective diethyl ether derivatives. Brief accounts of the work on furoguaiacidin³ and furoguaiacidin⁴ were reported earlier. In this paper we present a detailed account of the work on these lignans including the mechanistic aspects of the chemistry of these compounds.

Results and Discussion

Diethyl furoguaiacidin (1a), C₂₅H₃₀O₆ (M⁺ at *m/z* 426),

m.p. 135°, showed uv absorptions at λ_{max} 258 and 324 (log ε 4.16 and 4.50), which are strikingly similar to those of diethylfuroguaiacin (1c), the diethyl ether of the congener lignan, furoguaiacin¹ (1d), indicating the chromophoric similarity of the two compounds. The aromatic nature of 1a was indicated by its characteristic ir bands and by its mass spectrum showing only a few relatively less intense peaks.

The ¹H nmr spectrum of 1a showed signals for two aromatic methoxyls (δ 3.93, 6H, s) and two ethoxyl functions [δ 1.43 (6H, t, *J* 7 Hz) and 4.10 (4H, q, *J* 7 Hz)], an aromatic methyl (2.30, 3H s), an aliphatic methoxyl group (δ 3.43, 3H, s), two methylene protons of a methoxymethyl group linked to an aromatic nucleus (δ 4.45, 2H, s) and three pairs of aromatic protons at δ 6.90–7.40 (eight-line complex multiplet exhibiting ABX type of splitting patterns). The above ¹H nmr spectral data of 1a are strikingly similar to those of diethylfuroguaiacin (1c) except that the signal for one of the methyl groups at C-3 and C-4 of the latter is replaced by the signals for –CH₂OMe in the spectrum of the former. Based on the above spectral data, diethylfuroguaiacidin was assigned the structure 1a which was finally confirmed by its conversion to diethylfuroguaiacin (1c) by

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prolonged (26 h) hydrogenolysis over 10% Pd/C in EtOAc. Use of other solvents like EtOH or glacial HOAc resulted in no improvement in the rate of hydrogenolysis of **1a**. The reluctance of **1a** towards hydrogen uptake was attributed to the poor stability of methoxide radical. The parent lignan furoguaiacidin should, therefore, be represented by the structure **1b** which was also affirmed by the partial synthesis of its diethyl ether **1a** from **1c** (*vide infra*). Furoguaiacidin (**1b**) is thus the first furanoid lignan having a methoxymethyl substitution in the furan ring.

Diethylfuroguaiacidin (**2a**), m.p. 105°, was shown to have the molecular formula C₂₄H₂₈O₆ from elemental analysis and its mass spectrometrically derived molecular weight 412. This was also in conformity, within the limits of experimental error, with molecular weight determined by Rast method (409) and that in benzene at 40° (429). Compound **2a** showed uv absorptions at λ_{max} 230, 280 and 315 nm (log ε 4.33, 4.17 and 4.13), which are typical of 3,4-dioxygenated benzoyl chromophore. The ir spectrum of the compound showed, besides the characteristic bands for phenyl nucleus, a strong peak at ν_{max} 1635 cm⁻¹ which was attributed to a ketocarbonyl group, whose carbonyl charac-

ter was presumably reduced to a great extent by appreciable polarization of the carbon-oxygen double bond.

The ¹H nmr spectrum of **2a** showed signals for two 4-ethoxy-3-methoxybenzoyl moieties [δ 1.46 (6H, t, J 7 Hz), 4.10 (4H, q, J 7 Hz), 3.80 (6H, s), 6.75 (2H, d, J 8 Hz), 7.00 (2H, d, J 2 Hz) and 7.25 (2H, dd, J₁ 8 Hz and J₂ 2 Hz)] and two methyl groups (δ 2.16, 6H, s), each attached to sp² carbon atom. The above spectral data of diethylfuro-guaiacidin are intelligible in terms of a *cis*- or *trans*-enedione formulation **2a** or **3** for diethylfuro-guaiacidin. Other possible alternative structures **4**, **5**, **6** and **7**, considered initially for diethylfuroguaiacidin, were excluded in view of the (i) stability of the compound, (ii) failure of the compound to liberate iodine from an acidified solution of KI and to get reduced by Na₂SO₃ in CS₂, (iii) the results of molecular weight determination by Rast method and that in benzene at 45°, and (iv) the results of oxygen analysis (23.02%). The structure **2a** or **3** for diethylfuro-guaiacidin is also consistent with its mass spectral fragmentations showing intense peaks at m/z 179 and 151 corresponding to the ion-fragments **a** and **b**.

A decision between the alternative formulations **2a** and

- 1a** : R¹=Et, R²=OMe, R³=H
1b : R¹=H, R²=OMe, R³=H
1c : R¹=Et, R²=R³=H
1d : R¹=R²=R³=H
1e : R¹=Et, R²=R³=H, 2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-
1f : R¹=Et, R²=R³=OMe
1g : R¹=Et, R²=OEt, R³=H
1h : R¹=Et, R²=R³=OEt

- 2a** : R=Et
2b : R=H

- a** : R=Et (m/z 179)
b : R=H (m/z 151)

3 for diethylfuroguaiaoxidin was arrived at by the following transformation reactions. Diethylfuroguaiaoxidin which is stable below its melting point, when heated to 180° for 2 h, was converted to an isomeric compound, m.p. 167°. The uv, ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectra of the compound were strikingly similar to those of diethylfuroguaiaoxidin except that the ir absorption band for C=O group of the latter (ν_{\max} 1635 cm⁻¹) was shifted to higher frequency (1660 cm⁻¹) in the spectrum of the former and that while the vinyl methyl signal in the ¹H nmr spectrum of diethylfuroguaiaoxidin (δ 2.16) was shifted to a higher field (δ 1.80) in the spectrum of the product, the H-2' and H-6' of the latter showed a downfield shift (δ 7.56 and 7.60) compared to the corresponding protons of the former. These observations clearly suggest that diethylfuroguaiaoxidin and its thermal transformation product are geometrical isomers and that while the latter has the thermodynamically more stable *trans*-configuration **3**, diethylfuroguaiaoxidin must be the corresponding *cis*-isomer, represented by structure **2a**. This was further confirmed by the conversion of **3** to **2a** in ca. 50% yield upon irradiation of **3** to uv light⁵ at 253 nm for 4 h in THF. That **2a** is the *cis*-enedione isomer of the corresponding *trans*-isomer **3**, was also affirmed by the conversion of **2a** to **3**, when the former was heated under reflux with 10% methanolic KOH for 3 h. The above base-catalyzed isomerization of a *cis*-enedione to the corresponding *trans*-isomer finds analogy in the conversion⁶ of diethyl maleate to diethyl fumarate by means of secondary amines. A plausible mechanism of the above base-catalyzed isomerization of **2a** to **3** may be as shown in Scheme 1. The electrostatic repulsion of the assumed dianion **8** presumably facilitates the process of isomerization through rotation about 2,3-bond of **8**.

Scheme 1. Mechanism of base-catalyzed isomerization of **2a** to **3**.

The structure of diethylfuroguaiaoxidin (**2a**) was also supported by the following reductive transformations of the compound. Catalytic hydrogenation of **2a** with 10% Pd/C afforded diethylfuroguaiacin (**1c**) and its tetrahydro derivative **1e**, the diethyl ethers of the two congener lignans. Diethylfuroguaiaoxidin was also smoothly reduced to **1c** by (i) NaBH₄ in MeOH and (ii) Na₂S₂O₃ or Na₂SO₃ in glacial HOAc in presence of 6 N H₂SO₄ at room temperature. Under identical reaction conditions, the *trans*-isomer **3** failed to give **1c**. This may be ascribed to the fact that such reduction presumably involves a six-membered cyclic transition state which is only possible with the *cis*-enedione **2a** as shown in Scheme 2. Since **2a** contains an enedione function, it was expected to undergo reduction^{7,8} with zinc and HOAc. Thus, treatment of **2a** with zinc dust and 80% aque-

Scheme 2. Mechanism of reductive conversion of **2a** to **1c** by NaBH₄ and Na₂S₂O₃ or Na₂SO₃ / H⁽⁺⁾.

ous HOAc at 45–50° for 2 h afforded, besides **1c** as the major product, another compound, C₂₄H₃₀O₆, m.p. 185°, which from its various spectral data was shown to have the structure **9a**. The ir bands of the compound at ν_{\max} 3300 and 1670 cm⁻¹ and the presence of a six-proton distorted doublet at δ 1.1 in the absence of a two-proton quartet corresponding to the adjacent ketomethine protons in the ¹H nmr spectrum of the compound may be attributed to the system MeCH(C=O)–CH(C=O)Me, in which the two ketomethine protons are presumably undergoing alternate enolization. The above compound may, therefore, be assumed to remain in equilibrium between the keto (**9a**) and the two enol forms **9b** and **9c**. Mechanistically, the simultaneous formation of **1c** and **9a** in the reduction of **2a** with zinc and HOAc may be assumed to take place by the supply of electrons from zinc^{7,8} to give the species **10** which on successive cyclization and dehydration gives **1c**, and reduction without cyclization forms **9a** (Scheme 3; route-*a*). The formation of **1c** and **9a** from **2a** in the above reaction may also

be rationalized by an alternative mechanism involving the attack by zinc at the C-2 carbon atom (Scheme 3; route-*b*).

Under identical reaction conditions as employed for **2a**, the *trans*-enedione **3** also underwent smooth reduction with zinc and HOAc to give predominantly **1c** along with traces of **9a**. This reduction was also assumed to involve the transfer of electrons from zinc to give the species **11** which on rotation around 2,3-bond formed the intermediate **10** (generated from **2a**), the subsequent steps of the reaction being the same as in the case of **2a** (Scheme 3; route-*a*). The above reactions of **2a** and **3** thus provide a method for one-step conversion of enediones to the corresponding furans. The lower melting point of **2a** and the lower ir absorption frequency⁹ of its carbonyl function than those of **3** are also in conformity with the *cis*-configuration of **2a**.

Scheme 3. Mechanism of reductive conversion of **2a** and **3** by Zn and HOAc.

Since **2a** was converted to **1c** by a variety of reducing agents, it was thought that the reverse process could also be effected by suitable oxidants. One such oxidising agent is molecular oxygen which is reported^{8,10} to bring about oxidative transformations of simple furans or their alkyl and phenyl derivatives to the corresponding peroxides or

enediones under different reaction conditions. Molecular oxygen which normally exists in the triplet state, i.e. a diradical (**12**) is photochemically excited to the singlet state¹⁰ (**13**), the latter being formed more readily by microwave discharge. This form of singlet oxygen having a half-life in excess of 10^{-6} s is a highly reactive species which has been used in many oxidative reactions of substituted furans to enediones¹¹ and peroxides^{10,12}. However, by using high energy photosensitizers^{8,13-15} like eosin, rose Bengal, methylene blue and high reactant concentrations, a second excited state (**13**) of singlet oxygen, rapidly losing energy to form the more stable first excited state⁸ (**14**), has been used for the conversion of furan derivatives to the corresponding photoperoxides¹⁶. In view of the remarkable stability of diethylfuroguaiacin (**1c**) towards molecular oxygen in presence of ordinary light [**1c** remained unchanged even after prolonged passage of air through an alcoholic solution of the compound exposed to light from an ordinary electric lamp (100 W)], it was subjected to oxidation with molecular oxygen in presence of the photosensitizer eosin. Thus, when air was bubbled through an alcoholic solution of **1c** in presence of a little eosin, it was almost quantitatively converted to **2a** within 16 h. Mechanistically the above oxidative conversion of **1c** to **2a** may be assumed to involve 1,4-addition of the singlet oxygen (**13**) to **1c** leading to the unstable photoperoxide **6** which spontaneously decomposes successively to the hydroperoxy-oxonium species **15** and the hydroxy-oxonium ion **16**. Ring opening of the intermediate **16** ultimately leads to the formation of **2a** as shown in Scheme 4.

Other oxidants, viz. H_2O_2 ¹⁷, bromine¹⁸, HNO_3 ¹⁹ and ozone²⁰ have also been used for the conversion of furans to

Scheme 4. Mechanism of conversion of **1c** to **2a** by singlet oxygen and *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid.

enediones. But in most of these reactions the yields of the enediones were quite low due to the formation of other products caused by the participation of the protic solvent. Using *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid in nonprotic solvent like CHCl_3 at 0° for 12 h, we have been able to convert **1c** to **2a** in 70% yield. The formation of **2a** from **1c** in the above reaction may be assumed to take place by the direct formation of the hydroxy-oxonium ion **16** (Scheme 4). The above conversions of **1c** to **2a**, in effect, completed the synthesis of **2a**, since the dimethyl analogue of the former had already been synthesized by more conventional routes²¹.

Scheme 5. Mechanism of sequential introduction of alkoxy functions in the 3- and 4-methyl groups of 2,5-diaryl-3,4-dimethylfurans.

Further chemical evidence in support of the proposed structure of diethylfuroguaiacidin (**2a**) was provided by the following sequence of transformations involving the compound. Upon heating with methanolic H_2SO_4 , **2a** was readily converted to diethylfuroguaiacidin (**1a**). This, in turn, completed the partial synthesis of **1a** from **1c** via **2a**. Again, by bubbling air through an ethanolic solution of **1a** in presence of eosin followed by treatment of the product with methanolic H_2SO_4 afforded the 3,4-bis(methoxymethyl) analog **1f** of **1c**. The structure of **1f** was confirmed by its various spectral data particularly by its ^1H nmr spectrum which essentially differed from that of **1c** by the appearance of a four-proton singlet at δ 4.50 and a six-proton singlet at δ 3.50 for two CH_2OMe groups in the spectrum of **1f** in place of the six-proton singlet for the methyl groups at C-3 and C-4 of **1c**. The formation of **1f** from **1a** was assumed to involve the intermediacy of the enedione **2c** formed by photosensitized aerial oxidation of **1a**. In an analogous man-

ner, treatment of **2a** with ethanolic H_2SO_4 afforded the ethoxy analog **1g** of **1a**. The second ethoxy group was introduced in the 4-methyl group of **1g** by similar photosensitized air-oxidation of **1g** followed by treatment of the resultant enedione intermediate **2d** with ethanolic H_2SO_4 to give **1h**. The overall yields in the conversions of **2a** \rightarrow **1a** \rightarrow **1f** and **2a** \rightarrow **1g** \rightarrow **1h** were about 90%. The above transformations involving diethylfuroguaiacidin (**2a**), thus, not only provided further chemical evidence in support of its assigned structure, but also offered a very convenient general method for sequential introduction of alkoxy functions in the 3- and 4-methyl groups of 2,5-diaryl-3,4-dimethylfurans. Plausible mechanisms for the above transformations of **2a** are shown in Scheme 5.

Furoguaiacidin should, therefore, have structure **2b** and is the first member of an enedione lignan family. The possibility of its (as well as of furoguaiacidin **1b**) being a nonenzymic conversion product of **1c** seems unlikely in view of the stability of **1c** towards molecular oxygen in absence of a photosensitizer.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Silica gel (60–100 mesh) was used for column chromatography and silica gel G for tlc. Uv spectra were measured in 95% aldehyde-free EtOH and ir spectra in KBr disc. ^1H nmr spectra were measured at 60 MHz in CDCl_3 using TMS as the internal standard and mass spectra with a direct inlet system at 70 eV. All analytical samples were routinely dried over P_2O_5 for 24 h *in vacuo* and were tested for purity by tlc and MS. Na_2SO_4 was used for drying organic solvents and the petrol used had b.p. 60–80°.

Isolation of diethylfuroguaiacidin (1a), diethylfuroguaiacin (1c) and diethylfuroguaiacidin (2a): Air-dried finely powdered heartwood of *G. officinale* (2 kg) was soxhletted with petrol for 48 h. The defatted marc was then extracted with MeOH in the same soxhlet apparatus for 72 h. The MeOH extract was concentrated (100 ml), churned with 2 M NaOH solution (400 ml) and then filtered. The filtrate (deep bluish green in colour) was acidified in the cold with conc. HCl. The liberated solids were extracted with Et_2O , washed with H_2O , dried and the solvent removed. The gummy residue was dried in a vacuum desiccator. The dry gummy solid (30 g) was dissolved in acetone (400 ml), to which were added anhydrous K_2CO_3 (100 g) and EtI (50 ml) and the mixture was heated under reflux for 40 h on a water-bath. K_2CO_3 was filtered off. The filtrate was evaporated and the residue extracted with Et_2O and washed successively with 2 M NaOH and H_2O . The Et_2O layer was dried and the solvent removed. The residue was chromato-

graphed. The petrol-benzene (1 : 1) eluate gave a yellow semisolid mass which on crystallization from petrol-benzene mixture gave pure **1c** (1.5 g), m.p. 151° (Found: C, 72.70; H, 7.01. $C_{24}H_{28}O_5$ requires: C, 72.73; H, 7.07%); λ_{max} 252 and 326 nm (log ϵ 4.08 and 4.49); ν_{max} 1500, 1455, 1015 and 780 cm^{-1} .

The benzene eluate on evaporation gave a semisolid mass which was crystallized from petrol-benzene mixture to give pure **1a** (0.12 g) as light yellow granules, m.p. 135° (Found: C, 70.32; H, 7.10. $C_{25}H_{30}O_6$ requires: C, 70.42; H, 7.04%); produced deep red colouration with conc. H_2SO_4 ; λ_{max} 258 and 324 nm (log ϵ 4.16 and 4.50); ν_{max} 1600, 1580, 1510, 1038 and 785 cm^{-1} ; m/z (rel. int.) 426 [M^+] (100), 398 (11), 397 (33), 395 (7), 369 (7), 277 (10), 165 (13), 152 (11), 151 (24), 123 (9) and 108 (7).

Catalytic hydrogenation of diethylfuroguaiacidin (1a) : Compound **1a** (0.025 g) was dissolved in EtOAc (10 ml), to which was added 10% Pd/C (0.008 g). The mixture was stirred at room temperature in an atmosphere of hydrogen for 26 h. The catalyst was then filtered off and the filtrate was concentrated and chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate gave **1c** (0.015 g) which was crystallized from petrol-benzene mixture, m.p. 151°. Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (6 : 1) afforded unchanged **1a** (0.005 g).

Washing the main column with benzene-chloroform (4 : 1) gave a yellow gummy solid which was crystallized from petrol-ethyl acetate mixture to give pure **2a** (0.35 g) as colourless fine needles, m.p. 105° (Found: C, 70.00; H, 6.85; O, 23.02. $C_{24}H_{28}O_6$ requires: C, 69.90; H, 6.79; O, 23.30%); produced deep blue colouration with conc. H_2SO_4 ; λ_{max} 230, 280 and 315 nm (log ϵ 4.52, 4.21 and 4.17); ν_{max} 2980, 2930, 1635, 1575, 1500, 1455, 778 and 745 cm^{-1} ; m/z (rel. int.) 412 [M^+] (43), 384 (3), 261 (13), 246 (5), 245 (27), 233 (17), 218 (7), 217 (36), 191 (8), 180 (25), 179 (100), 152 (13), 151 (99), 123 (17) and 108 (10).

Thermal treatment of diethylfuroguaiacidin (2a) : **2a** (0.12 g) was heated in an oil-bath (170–180°) for 2 h. The product after cooling was extracted with $CHCl_3$, dried, concentrated and chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (8 : 1) eluate gave **3** (0.10 g), which was crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture as fine needles, m.p. 167° (Found: C, 69.82; H, 6.85. $C_{24}H_{28}O_6$ requires: C, 69.90; H, 6.79%); produced a straw yellow colouration with conc. H_2SO_4 ; λ_{max} 235, 286 and 308 nm (log ϵ 4.53, 4.32 and 4.34); ν_{max} 1660, 1590, 1580, 1032 and 778 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ 1.50, 6H, t, J 7 Hz and 4.23, 4H, q, J 7 Hz (Ar-OCH₂CH₃), 1.80 (6H, s, CH₃-C=C-CH₃), 3.96 (6H, s, ArOCH₃), 6.86 (2H, d, J 10 Hz, H-5'), 7.56, (2H, br s, H-6') and 7.60 (2H, dd, J_1 10 Hz and J_2 3 Hz, H-2'); m/z (rel. int.) 412 [M^+] (47),

261 (16), 245 (7), 233 (26), 217 (15), 179 (100), 180 (16), 152 (10), 151 (71), 123 (22) and 108 (7).

Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (6 : 1) afforded unchanged **2a** (0.01 g).

Irradiation of 3 with uv light : A solution of **3** (0.02 g) in THF (15 ml) was exposed to uv light (at 253 nm) for 4 h with stirring. The residue after removal of the solvent was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate gave unchanged **3** (0.008 g). Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (8 : 1) afforded **2a** (0.01 g) which was crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 105°.

Conversion of 2a to 3 by methanolic KOH : A solution of **2a** (0.025 g) in 10% methanolic KOH (15 ml) was heated on a boiling water-bath for 3 h. MeOH was then removed under reduced pressure. The residue was treated with H_2O , extracted with Et_2O , washed, dried and the solvent removed. The residue was chromatographed. The early fractions of the petrol-EtOAc (8 : 1) eluate gave **3** (0.015 g). The later fractions of the same eluate gave traces of uncharacterized solid. Further elution of the column afforded unchanged **2a** (0.005 g).

Catalytic hydrogenation of 2a : To a solution of **2a** (0.10 g) in EtOAc taken in a 50 ml flask was added 10% Pd/C (0.03 g). The flask was evacuated and a stream of hydrogen was passed into it at room temperature for 3 h under constant stirring. The catalyst was then filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated and chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate gave **1c** (0.04 g), which was crystallized from petrol-benzene mixture, m.p. 151°. Further washing the column with petrol-EtOAc (9 : 1) afforded **1e** (0.05 g) which was crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 105° (Found: C, 71.90; H, 8.08. $C_{24}H_{32}O_5$ requires: C, 72.00, H, 8.00%); produced pink colouration with conc. H_2SO_4 ; λ_{max} 233 and 278 nm (log ϵ 4.04 and 3.71); 1H nmr δ 0.62, 6H, d, J 7 Hz and 2.67, 2H, m (CH₃-C=C-CH₃), 1.47, 6H, t, J 7 Hz and 4.10, 4H, q, J 7 Hz (Ar-OCH₂-CH₃), 3.90 (6H, s, ArOCH₃), 5.1 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, H-2 and H-5) and 6.75–7.20 (6H, m, ArH).

Reduction of 2a with NaBH₄ : To a solution of **2a** (0.02 g) in MeOH (15 ml) was added $NaBH_4$ (0.05 g) in small portions. The mixture was left overnight. MeOH was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was treated with H_2O , extracted with $CHCl_3$, washed with H_2O , dried and the solvent removed. The residue on crystallization from petrol-benzene mixture gave **1c** (0.018 g).

Reduction of 2a with Na₂S₂O₃ and Na₂SO₃ in acid medium : To a solution of **2a** (0.02 g) in glacial HOAc (20 ml) was added 6 *N* aq. H_2SO_4 (1 ml). The solution turned turbid. Another 10 ml of glacial HOAc was added to make a clear solution. The mixture was kept for 5 min. To this

acidified solution was then added a saturated aq. solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ (20 ml). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 10–15 min and then diluted with water and finally extracted with Et_2O . The Et_2O extract was washed with NaHCO_3 solution and then with H_2O , dried and the solvent removed. The residue was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate gave **1c** (0.016 g). Further washing the column with petrol-EtOAc (6 : 1) afforded unchanged **2a** (0.002 g).

Following the same method as above **2a** (0.02 g) was subjected to reduction with a saturated aq. solution of Na_2SO_3 (10 ml). After 10–15 min, the reaction products were worked up in the same manner as above. Chromatography of the products gave **1c** (0.014 g) and unchanged **2a** (0.003 g).

Reduction of 2a with zinc and HOAc : To a solution of **2a** (0.02 g) in 80% aq. HOAc (15 ml) was added zinc dust (1.0 g). The mixture was kept at room temperature overnight. The mixture was stirred at 45–50° for 2 h and then diluted with H_2O and extracted with CHCl_3 . The CHCl_3 extract was washed with H_2SO_4 , dried and the solvent removed. The residue was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate gave **1c** (0.008 g). Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (8 : 1) afforded **9a** (0.008 g) which was crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 185° (Found : C, 69.45; H, 7.19. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_6$ requires : C, 69.56; H, 7.24%); produced pink colouration changing to green with conc. H_2SO_4 ; λ_{max} 207, 232, 280 and 310 nm (log ϵ 4.14, 4.18, 4.06 and 4.01); ν_{max} 3300, 1670, 1575, 1520, 1040, 804 and 783 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 1.10 (6H, distorted doublet, 3- and 4-Me), 1.50, 6H, t, J 7 Hz and 4.20, 4H, q, J 7 Hz (ArO- CH_2 - CH_3), 3.96 (6H, s, ArOCH₃), 6.91 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, H-5'), 7.61 (2H, br s, H-2') and 7.70 (2H, dd, J_1 9 Hz and J_2 2.5 Hz, H-6'); m/z (rel. int.) 414 [M^+] (40), 235 (10), 208 (4), 194 (11), 181 (4), 180 (34), 179 (100), 152 (7), 151 (79), 123 (22), 108 (7), 91 (4), 77 (6), 67 (4), 65 (6) and 55 (6).

Reduction of 3 with zinc and HOAc : To a solution of **3** (0.02 g) in 80% aq. HOAc (15 ml) was added zinc dust (1.0 g). The reaction was carried out under identical condition as employed for **2a** and worked up in the same manner. The products were chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate gave **1c** (0.01 g). Elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (9 : 1) afforded traces of **9a**. The petrol-EtOAc (6 : 1) gave unreacted **3** (0.004 g).

Oxidation of 1c to 2a by air in presence of eosin : To a solution of **1c** (0.10 g) in absolute EtOH (25 ml) was added eosin (0.004 g). Air was drawn through this solution for 18 h at room temperature by means of a capillary operating under water-suction. Fresh amount of ethanol was added from time to time to keep the reaction mixture in solution.

After the reaction, alcohol was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was treated with H_2O (15 ml) and extracted with CHCl_3 . The CHCl_3 extract was dried and the solvent removed. The residue was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (6 : 1) eluate gave **2a** (0.09 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 105°.

Oxidation of 1c to 2a with m-chloroperbenzoic acid : To a solution of **1c** (0.10 g) in dry CHCl_3 (15 ml) at 0–5° was added *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (0.05 g) and the reaction mixture was kept at that temperature for 12 h. The colour of the solution changed to yellow. The reaction mixture was then treated with H_2O (20 ml) and extracted with CHCl_3 . The CHCl_3 extract was first washed with NaHCO_3 solution to free it from acid and then with H_2O , dried and the solvent removed. The residue was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate gave unreacted **1c** (0.01 g). Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (6 : 1) afforded **2a** (0.07 g).

Treatment of 2a with methanolic H_2SO_4 : A solution of **2a** (0.10 g) in methanol (20 ml) was treated with 6 *N* aq. H_2SO_4 (2 ml). The mixture was gently refluxed on a water-bath for 20 min. MeOH was then removed under reduced pressure, the residue treated with ice-water and extracted with CHCl_3 . The CHCl_3 extract was first washed with NaHCO_3 solution to free it from acid and then with H_2O , dried and the solvent removed. The residue was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate gave **1a** (0.085 g), which was crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 135°.

Conversion of 1a to 1f : To a solution of **1a** (0.05 g) in absolute EtOH (50 ml) was added eosin (0.002 g). Air was bubbled through this solution for 18 h adding occasionally fresh amount of EtOH as in the case of the conversion of **1c** to **2a**. The reaction product was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (2 : 1) eluate gave **2c** (0.045 g) as amorphous solid; λ_{max} 232, 281 and 314 nm (log ϵ 4.16, 4.30 and 4.50).

A solution of **2c** (0.04 g) in MeOH (8 ml) was treated with 6 *N* H_2SO_4 (0.9 ml). The mixture was gently refluxed for 20 min and worked up in the same manner as in the case of the conversion of **2a** to **1a**. The crude reaction product was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (5 : 1) eluate gave **1f** (0.03 g) which was crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 125° (Found : C, 68.30; H, 7.00. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_7$ requires : C, 68.42; H, 7.02%); produced greenish yellow colouration with conc. H_2SO_4 ; λ_{max} 260 and 322 nm (log ϵ 4.17 and 4.44); ν_{max} 1602, 1585, 1038 and 778 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 1.50, 6H, t, J 7 Hz and 4.16, 4H, q, J 7 Hz (Ar-OCH₂CH₃), 3.96 (6H, s, ArOMe), 3.50, 6H, s and 4.50, 4H, s (furan-CH₂-OCH₃) and 6.90–7.40 (6H, m, ArH); m/z (rel. int.) 456 [M^+] (100), 428 (25), 427 (76), 426 (40),

400 (25), 399 (17), 398 (17), 230 (10), 201 (18), 179 (10), 169 (30), 1.65 (10), 152 (12), 151 (18), 137 (10) and 123 (10).

Conversion of 2a to 1g : To a solution of 2a (0.10 g) in absolute EtOH (20 ml) was added 6 N H₂SO₄ (2 ml). The mixture was gently refluxed for 20 min and worked up in the same manner as in the case of the conversion of 2a to 1a. The crude product was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (12 : 1) gave 1g (0.08 g) which was crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 110° (Found : C, 70.80; H, 7.30. C₂₆H₃₂O₆ requires : C, 70.91; H, 7.27%); produced reddish green colouration with conc. H₂SO₄; λ_{max} 255 and 322 nm (log ε 3.84 and 4.16); ν_{max} 1590, 1580, 1040 and 780 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ 1.48, 6H, t, J 7 Hz and 4.15, 4H, q, J 7 Hz (Ar-OCH₂-CH₃), 3.93 (6H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 2.28 (3H, s, furan-CH₃), 1.28, 3H, t, J 7 Hz, 3.63, 2H, q, J 7 Hz and 4.45, 2H, s (furan-CH₂-OCH₂CH₃); m/z (rel. int.) 440 [M⁺] (100), 412 (48), 395 (8), 383 (3), 367 (4), 365 (5), 337 (3), 307 (3), 277 (3), 192 (8), 151 (8) and 123 (3).

Conversion of 1f to 1h : Air was bubbled through a solution of 1f (0.05 g) in absolute EtOH (80 ml) containing eosin (0.002 g) for 18 h as in the case of the conversion of 1c to 2a and the final reaction product was worked up in the same manner as in the above case. Column chromatography of the crude product gave pure 2d (0.045 g) as an amorphous solid; λ_{max} 231, 281 and 316 nm (log ε 4.20, 4.35 and 4.55).

To a solution of 2d (0.04 g) in absolute EtOH (6 ml) was added 6 N H₂SO₄ (1 ml) and the mixture was gently refluxed for 20 min. The reaction product was worked up as in the case of the conversion of 2c to 1f. The crude product was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (8 : 1) eluate gave 1h (0.035 g) which was crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 125° (Found : C, 69.30; H, 7.50. C₂₈H₃₆O₇ requires : C, 69.42; H, 7.44%); produced a dirty green colouration with conc. H₂SO₄; λ_{max} 260 and 321 nm (log ε 4.17 and 4.43); ν_{max} 1600, 1585, 1035 and 778 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ 1.48, 6H, t, J 7 Hz and 4.16, 4H, q, J 7 Hz (Ar-OCH₂CH₃), 3.96 (6H, s, ArOCH₃), 1.27, 6H, t, J 7 Hz, 3.65, 4H, q, J 7 Hz and 4.55, 4H, s (furan-CH₂-OCH₂CH₃) and 6.88–7.38 (6H, m, ArH); m/z (rel. int.) 484 [M⁺] (100), 456 (5), 455 (17), 410 (3), 409 (8), 395 (5), 179 (8), 165 (4), 161 (4), 151 (12), 149 (3), 137 (3), 123 (4), 103 (3), 75 (4) and 59 (10).

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